

CFD Investigation of Turbulent Dissipation Rates in Peripheral Pumps for Micromixing

Thomas Reviol ^{1,*}, Arvid Kraus ^{2,3}, Seyedeh-Saba Ashrafmansouri ^{2,4}, Erik von Harbou ²

¹Fluid Mechanics and Energy Technology Group, RPTU University Kaiserslautern-Landau, Kaiserslautern, Germany

²Laboratory of Reaction and Fluid Process Engineering, RPTU University Kaiserslautern-Landau, Kaiserslautern, Germany

³Flow Processes, Fraunhofer Institute for Industrial Mathematics ITWM, Kaiserslautern, Germany

⁴Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Larestan, Lar, Iran

*Corresponding author: lrf-pub@mv.rptu.de

Contributor Roles Taxonomy

Thomas Reviol: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing - original draft, Writing - review and editing

Arvid Kraus: Conceptualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing - review and editing

Seyedeh-Saba Ashrafmansouri: Conceptualization, Writing - review and editing

Erik von Harbou: Conceptualization, Resources, Supervision, Writing - review and editing

Keywords

Peripheral Pumps, Micromixing, Turbulent Dissipation Rate, Computational Fluid Dynamics, URANS, Kolmogorov Scales, Mixing Efficiency

Abstract

Peripheral pumps are promising micromixing devices due to their intricate internal flow structures and elevated turbulent dissipation rates. This study presents a detailed computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis of turbulent dissipation in a peripheral pump, employing transient unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) simulations with the k - ω Shear Stress Transport (SST) turbulence model.

The analysis reveals that peripheral pumps can achieve exceptionally high turbulent dissipation rates up to 6000 W kg^{-1} , comparable to specialized high-shear mixers despite operating at moderate Reynolds numbers in the range 3.1×10^4 to 5.5×10^4 .

The highest dissipation rates are localized within the impeller blade passages, driven by characteristic flow exchange between the impeller and sidechannel, in the breaker channel, and in zones of elevated dissipation and distinctive formation patterns downstream in the breaker channel wake.

Kolmogorov scale analysis reveals extensive regions with $\eta < 5 \mu\text{m}$ and $\tau_\eta < 1 \text{ ms}$, which indicates sensitivity to the shaft speed, but is largely unaffected by volumetric flow rate. In contrast, mixing efficiency, which is defined as the ratio of the power associated with the turbulent dissipation rate to the hydraulic power input and ranges from 20 % to 55 %, decreases slowly with increasing flow rate and is nearly unaffected by shaft speed.

The study establishes that peripheral pumps offer significant potential as micromixing devices, achieving performance levels comparable to dedicated high-shear mixers while providing operational flexibility and unique flow characteristics. These findings support the application of peripheral pumps in processes requiring intense mixing at small scales, particularly in chemical and pharmaceutical industries.

1. Introduction

Many industrial reaction systems are highly sensitive to mixing [1–3]. These systems, known as mixing-controlled reactions, have a reaction time constant that is comparable to or shorter than the mixing time constant at the microscale. In such fast reactions, micromixing – the process of mixing different species at the molecular level – becomes crucial, as enhanced mixing at microscales can significantly improve the selectivity for the desired products [4].

Although a wide range of well-known mixing technologies can be found in the literature, micromixing demands remain challenging. Conventional mixing equipment is mostly unsuitable for achieving the required conditions, as effective micromixing demands length and time scales of the process close to the Kolmogorov scales. Furthermore, high volumetric turbulent dissipation rates are essential [4–6], which necessitate specialized mixing technologies.

The most common mixing devices are stirred tanks (ST), static mixers (SM), rotor-stator mixers (RSM), and micromixers. Numerous studies have investigated mixers and turbulent energy dissipation rates ε in various geometries and under different conditions. A brief overview of some relevant studies is provided in Table 1.1, which contains reactor types, the achieved dissipation rates at the investigated Reynolds numbers, and the type of investigation.

Table 1.1.: Comparison of the performance of different mixers for the mixing process.

Research Group	Reactor Type	ε (W kg^{-1})	Reynolds Number	Type of Investigation
Kresta <i>et al.</i> [7]	ST	<0.1	N/A	CFD
Hartmann <i>et al.</i> [8]	ST	<0.1	≈ 7000	Exp. & CFD
Azizi <i>et al.</i> [9]	SMX+ mixer	ca. 300	$[0.4, 1.2] \times 10^3$	CFD
Albertazzi <i>et al.</i> [10]	SM	$<7 \times 10^2$	$[0.7, 1.6] \times 10^4$	CFD
Meng <i>et al.</i> [11]	Komax SM	1 to 10	$[0.26, 1.8] \times 10^4$	Exp. & CFD
Chabanon <i>et al.</i> [12]	SMX+ mixer	ca. 1000	2700	Exp.
He <i>et al.</i> [13]	screen-type SM	<1000	$[0.6, 1.3] \times 10^3$	CFD
Espinoza <i>et al.</i> [14]	RSM	300	$[1.2, 4.2] \times 10^5$	Exp.
Minnick <i>et al.</i> [15]	RSM	100	$[0.58, 1.2] \times 10^5$	Exp. & CFD
Vasilev <i>et al.</i> [16]	pulsating flow apparatus	ca. 1000	$[0.2, 1] \times 10^5$	Exp.
You <i>et al.</i> [17]	microfluidic mixer	<10 000	4500	Exp. & CFD

STs are widely used in large-scale processes, but they are less suitable for micromixing due to their macro-scale flow patterns and lower local dissipation rates ($\varepsilon = 0.01 \text{ W kg}^{-1}$ to 1 W kg^{-1}) [7, 8, 18]. SMs are energy-efficient and simple to operate, with moderate effectiveness for micromixing, but they are generally limited by their passive nature, which restricts their ability to

achieve the rapid and thorough molecular mixing required in micromixing process. Moreover, the flexibility of SMs is limited by their geometry, and scalability can be challenging. When considering micromixing applications, RSMs and micromixers stand out due to their ability to generate high shear rates and intense local turbulence, making them highly effective for rapid and uniform molecular-level mixing [5, 19]. RSMs offer the advantage of high energy dissipation, enabling effective micromixing at industrial scales, but they can be energy-intensive, may cause shear-sensitive materials to degrade, and often require complex equipment and maintenance. Micromixers, on the other hand, are specifically designed for precise micromixing at small scales, providing excellent control over mixing times and minimizing dead zones; however, their small dimensions limit throughput and they can be complex to scale up for large-volume processes.

Collectively, all the above-mentioned mixers underscore the complex dependence of dissipation rates on geometry and Reynolds number. As Reynolds numbers are calculated either as pipe or impeller Reynolds numbers, direct comparison is challenging. Nevertheless, dissipation rates can be broadly classified as follows: $< 10 \text{ W kg}^{-1}$ for low rates, $10 \text{ W kg}^{-1} < \varepsilon < 100 \text{ W kg}^{-1}$ for moderate rates, $100 \text{ W kg}^{-1} < \varepsilon < 10\,000 \text{ W kg}^{-1}$ for high rates, and $> 10\,000 \text{ W kg}^{-1}$ for the highest rates. [7–17]

Peripheral pumps, though unconventional as mixing reactors, exhibit highly complex internal flow fields that are advantageous for micromixing applications. Their main advantage over RSMs and micromixers for micromixing process is that peripheral pumps offer a wide operating range by adjusting flow rates and rotational speeds, a robust design suitable for industrial environments, and moderate Reynolds numbers that enable practical implementation.

Originating from fluid machinery, peripheral pumps are primarily valued for their self-priming capabilities but are characterized by low hydraulic efficiency. This apparent disadvantage becomes beneficial for micromixing applications: peripheral pumps utilize a distinctive mechanism called internal multistaging to achieve pressure rise through repeated exchange of fluid between the impeller and sidechannel. While this process successfully generates the desired pressure increase, it simultaneously produces high turbulence intensities as an inherent side effect, converting the portion of inlet mechanical energy that cannot be transformed to pressure rise into turbulent dissipation. Specifically, impeller-sidechannel interaction creates complex 3D flow patterns, the breaker channel generates high local shear rates, and tubular vortical structures in blade passages further enhance mixing. The resulting energy transfer to smaller scales via the Kolmogorov cascade enhances mixing at the molecular level, enabling simultaneous pumping and mixing functionality in a single device with continuous operation and no flow interruption. The potential of peripheral pumps for micromixing process has been demonstrated by Ashrafmansouri *et al.* [4] using the Villermaux-Dushman reaction. Nevertheless, a comprehensive understanding of the internal flow field and its impact on micromixing remains to be established.

Previous studies on the fluid dynamics of peripheral pumps have investigated the flow dynamics and geometric optimization of this pump type, but particularly of sidechannel pumps, providing valuable insights into their internal mechanisms [20–22]. However, these studies typically focus on optimization of hydraulic performance rather than mixing efficiency in peripheral pumps and its physical mechanisms.

The primary objective of this study is to provide a quantitative evaluation of local turbulent dis-

sipation rates and Kolmogorov scales throughout the entire flow domain of a peripheral pump, thereby establishing its micromixing capability. Since mixing-sensitive reactions proceed extremely fast and locally, global energy dissipation is insufficient for process design, which depends critically on local flow velocities and energy dissipation rates at the feed. Due to the small sizes of both the pump and the flow structures to be observed, experimental measurement techniques are highly challenging and therefore limited. Consequently, transient computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations are applied to gain non-invasive insights through detailed spatial and temporal characterization of the flow field, which is essential for understanding the mechanisms governing mixing at microscales.

Simulating peripheral pumps presents significant challenges due to their complex geometry and inherently transient flow phenomena. To address these complexities while maintaining computational feasibility, unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) simulations are favored against Large Eddy Simulations (LES). The $k-\omega$ Shear Stress Transport (SST) turbulence model is selected based on its demonstrated reliability in similar pump applications [21, 22]. Model validation is performed against manufacturer data to ensure credibility of the numerical results.

The study incorporates a fully resolved pump geometry and investigates a range of operating conditions, specifically volumetric flow rates of 1 L h^{-1} , 10 L h^{-1} , 20 L h^{-1} , 40 L h^{-1} and 80 L h^{-1} and rotational speeds of 2070 min^{-1} , 2880 min^{-1} and 3690 min^{-1} . Thus, the investigated impeller Reynolds numbers range from 3.1×10^4 to 5.5×10^4 . Particular emphasis is placed on the spatial distribution of turbulent energy dissipation rates and Kolmogorov length and time scales across the flow domain, as these parameters are critical for assessing micromixing efficiency under varying operational regimes.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Pump Under Consideration

The pump investigated in this study is a peripheral pump, model HMR-020, manufactured by Fink Chem+Tech GmbH, identical to the pump examined by Ashrafmansouri *et al.* [4]. This work focuses on the hydraulic components of the pump; therefore, a concise overview of its design and operational principles is provided. Originally developed for application as a mixing reactor in the chemical industry, the pump features two inlets: the primary inlet (referred to as “inlet”) and a secondary inlet (“feed”). To prevent fluid contamination, the pump employs a magnetic coupling between stator and rotor of the motor, with a containment shell providing isolation. Fig. 2.1a presents a front view photograph of the pump, highlighting the two inlets and the outlet. For enhanced optical accessibility, the original housing was replaced with a transparent version, allowing visualization of the impeller and sidechannel. The impeller is shown separately in Fig. 2.1b for clarity. It should be noted that certain components, such as the containment shell, connection ports to the motor cavity, and the motor itself, are not depicted in the figures.

(a) Front view of the peripheral pump, illustrating the primary and secondary inlets, outlet, and principal components.

(b) Isolated view of the impeller, highlighting the blade arrangement and central disc structure.

Figure 2.1.: Overview of the investigated peripheral pump (model HMR-020, Fink Chem+Tech GmbH): (a) front view with key components, (b) impeller geometry.

Fig. 2.1b reveals that the impeller comprises 36 blades enclosed centrally by a disc structure, effectively partitioning the blades into two separate blade passages. Consequently, each side of the impeller operates with its own dedicated sidechannel. The sidechannel itself extends

continuously over the entire width and spans an angular range of 315° from the inlet to the outlet. The feed inlet is positioned 45° relative to the primary inlet. The continuity of the side channel is interrupted by the breaker channel, which separates the suction and pressure sides and subtends an angle of 45° . For subsequent analysis of volumetric dissipation, the internal volumes of the pump are of interest: The total internal volume is 5.2 mL, with the impeller, sidechannel, and breaker channel together comprising 2.83 mL. The impeller gap – the clearance between the housing and impeller shaft – accounts for 0.13 mL, while the remaining cavity around the motor (motor gap) has an approximate volume of 2.25 mL. Key geometric parameters are summarized in Tab. S.1 in Appendix S.1.

The manufacturer specifies the design point of the pump at a volumetric flow rate of 10 L h^{-1} and a shaft speed of 2880 min^{-1} . At this operating condition, the data sheet reports a head of approximately 5.5 m. Fig. 2.2 presents the manufacturer’s curve, highlighting the design point. As can be seen, the shut-off head (zero-flow condition) and one additional partial load point at 5 L h^{-1} are provided, as well as the overload regime, which is characterized by three further operating points: 20 L h^{-1} , 40 L h^{-1} and 80 L h^{-1} .

Figure 2.2.: Performance characteristics of the investigated peripheral pump (model HMR-020, Fink Chem+Tech GmbH) as provided by the manufacturer. Markers denote experimentally determined operating points.

2.2. Numerical Setup

To analyze the peripheral pump described, a CFD URANS simulation was conducted using the open-source software OpenFOAM[®] v2306 (ESI Group). The computational domain encompasses the complete pump geometry, including the impeller, sidechannel, breaker channel, motor cavity, and all associated gaps. The simulation was run using the OpenFOAM standard solver pimpleFoam, which is suitable for transient, incompressible flows with dynamic meshes and large time steps. The subsequent sections provide a detailed account of the numerical setup.

2.2.1. Meshing

Mesh generation was performed using the commercial software ANSYS ICEM CFD (version 2022 R2). Owing to the geometric symmetry of the pump, a meshing strategy based on rotationally periodic segments was adopted. Fig. 2.3 presents the partially sectioned mesh prior to assembly of the full domain. The back view (Fig. 2.3a) highlights the motor cavity in the foreground, with the hydraulic components situated posteriorly. The front view (Fig. 2.3b) displays the impeller, sidechannel, and breaker channel; the impeller gap is clearly visible in this perspective, while the motor gap is partially obscured. Both perspectives reveal the connection passages between the main pump body and the motor cavity. By applying rotational and mirror symmetry operations, the complete computational domain is reconstructed from the displayed segments. To ensure the development of fully established flow profiles at the domain boundaries, the inlet and outlet pipes were extended axially. An axial length of $10 \cdot D$, where D is the pipe diameter, was selected for both inflow and outflow sections.

Figure 2.3.: Partially cut mesh of the pump.

Given that the primary objective of this study is the accurate characterization of the turbulent dissipation rate ε , the computational mesh must be sufficiently refined to resolve turbulent length scales smaller than the integral length scale l_0 , which marks the onset of the inertial subrange. Furthermore, to ensure complete resolution of the boundary layer, the mesh was refined such that the dimensionless wall distance y^+ consistently falls within the range of 1 to 5, with a target value close to unity.

Applying the above described meshing methodology facilitates the creation of a high-quality, fully hexahedral mesh with a relatively low overall cell count, while enabling focused local refinement in regions of specific interest. The final mesh comprises approximately 5.7×10^6 hexahedral cells, with boundary layers fully resolved at all solid surfaces.

2.2.2. Boundary Conditions

A precise and rigorous specification of physical boundary conditions is essential to ensure the reliability and accuracy of the numerical simulations. Given the geometric and operational complexity of the peripheral pump, a range of boundary conditions is imposed on the various

Figure 2.4.: Total overview of the computational domain, gaps, and interfaces including all boundary patches.

surfaces of the computational domain. A detailed overview of the applied boundary conditions is provided in Fig. 2.4, which illustrates the locations of all inlets, outlets, wall boundaries, gaps, and interface regions within the computational domain. Tab. 2.1 systematically summarizes the boundary condition types assigned to each surface patch.

Table 2.1.: Overview of the boundary conditions applied to the various patches of the computational domain.

Patch	Type
IN	main inflow
FEED	secondary inflow, neglected
OUT	outflow
IMPELLER	rotating wall
WALL	stationary wall
WALL_MOVING	rotating wall
ACMI_IMPELLER_SIDECHANNEL_HOUSING_MOV	interface/wall
ACMI_IMPELLER_SIDECHANNEL_HOUSING_STAT	interface/wall
ACMI_IMPELLER_SIDECHANNEL_MOTOR_MOV	interface/wall
ACMI_IMPELLER_SIDECHANNEL_MOTOR_STAT	interface/wall
AMI_IMPELLER_GAP	interface
AMI_IMPELLER_SIDECHANNEL	interface

Inflow and outflow conditions

As can be seen in Fig. 2.4a, the pump features two inlets, designated as IN (main inlet) and FEED (secondary inlet). For both inlets, the velocity boundary condition is prescribed using the `flowRateInletVelocity` formulation. In the present study, the secondary inlet FEED is not utilized and is therefore set to a volumetric flow rate of 0 L h^{-1} . The main inlet IN, by contrast, is assigned a volumetric flow rate corresponding to the specific operating point under investigation, spanning a range from 1 L h^{-1} to 80 L h^{-1} . For both inlets, a `zeroGradient` boundary condition is imposed for pressure, permitting the pressure field to adapt in response to the internal flow solution. Turbulence quantities at the inlets are prescribed according to established relations [23]: The turbulent kinetic energy k is computed as $k = 1.5 (I \cdot U_\infty)^2$, and the turbulent dissipation rate ε is evaluated as $\varepsilon = C_\mu \cdot k^{1.5} / l$. Here, I denotes the turbulence intensity, set to $I = 0.05$, U_∞ is the mean inlet velocity determined from the volumetric flow rate \dot{V} , l represents the turbulence length scale, defined as $l = 0.07 \cdot D$ and C_μ is a constant, typically set to 0.09. The turbulent viscosity ν_t is considered as zero in the inlet boundary condition.

The outlet (OUT) employs a `pressureInletOutletVelocity` condition for velocity, permitting both outflow and potential backflow. The static pressure is prescribed via a `fixedValue` condition, set to zero gauge pressure due to the incompressibility assumption. Turbulence quantities at the outlet are specified using the `inletOutlet` condition, which applies the internal field value for outflow and the inlet value for backflow. The turbulent viscosity is similarly treated with the `inletOutlet` condition but set to zero for backflow.

Wall conditions

The wall surfaces of the pump are classified into three principal categories. The first category comprises surfaces in rotational motion, including the impeller, motor, and hub. The impeller surface is denoted as `IMPELLER`, while the rotating walls of the motor and hub are collectively designated as `WALL_MOVING`. The second category encompasses the stationary walls of the housing and sidechannel, labeled as `WALL`. All wall surfaces are shown in Fig. 2.4a.

Specifically, the impeller and all rotating components are assigned a `movingWallVelocity` boundary condition for velocity, reflecting their rotational motion. The angular velocity is prescribed according to the shaft speed investigated, which ranges from 2070 min^{-1} to 3690 min^{-1} in this study. All other wall surfaces are treated as stationary. For pressure, a `zeroGradient` condition is imposed on all wall boundaries, consistent with the assumption that the far-field pressure is transmitted to the wall. Turbulence quantities at the walls are specified using either a `fixedValue` condition, owing to the fully resolved boundary layer, or a `nutkWallFunction` for the turbulent viscosity.

Interface and combined conditions

The third category of wall surfaces comprises dynamic interfaces between the impeller and sidechannel (Fig. 2.4b to Fig. 2.4d). Due to the sidechannel interruption at the breaker channel, the circumferential surface of the impeller domain alternates between interface and wall

functions, depending on impeller position. This is implemented using the `cyclicACMI` condition with paired moving and stationary patches (Fig. 2.4d). The radial surface constitutes a special case: the breaker channel is meshed as a thin shell and treated with the `cyclicAMI` condition. The `AMI_IMPELLER_GAP` patch connects the impeller gap to the sidechannel, while `AMI_IMPELLER_SIDECHANNEL` links the sidechannel to the motor gap (Fig. 2.4c).

As described above, `cyclicACMI` patches – specifically, `ACMI_IMPELLER_SIDECHANNEL_HOUSING` and `ACMI_IMPELLER_SIDECHANNEL_MOTOR` – constitute paired moving and stationary interfaces. Their function alternates dynamically between acting as a wall or as an interface, depending on the instantaneous angular position of the impeller. When the `cyclicACMI` patch act as wall surfaces, a `noSlip` boundary condition is applied for velocity and a `zeroGradient` condition for pressure. For all turbulence quantities except the turbulent viscosity, a `fixedValue` condition is imposed, initialized with the inlet values and subsequently allowed to evolve during the simulation. The turbulent viscosity is specified using the `nutkWallFunction` to ensure appropriate near-wall modeling.

2.2.3. Turbulence Modeling and Fluid Properties

The selection of an appropriate turbulence model is crucial for accurate flow predictions. Given the computational constraints (5.7×10^6 cells) and the requirement for time-resolved results, a URANS approach was chosen over LES. The $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model [24] was selected as it combines the advantages of the $k-\epsilon$ model in the free stream with superior near-wall treatment of the $k-\omega$ model. This hybrid approach improves turbulence prediction accuracy in complex flow scenarios, particularly within peripheral pumps. The $k-\omega$ SST model requires fully resolved boundary layers with y^+ values in the range 1 to 5, which is ensured by the meshing strategy.

The working fluid is modeled as incompressible, isothermal, and Newtonian. Given the simplicity of the fluid system, only the kinematic viscosity is required. According to [25], a kinematic viscosity of $1.003 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ is adopted, corresponding to water at 293.15 K. It should be noted that OpenFOAM treats incompressible flows by normalizing the pressure with respect to density. The fluid density at the specified temperature is 998.21 kg m^{-3} .

2.2.4. Numerical Methods

The discretization follows established OpenFOAM best practices, employing second-order schemes where feasible while ensuring numerical stability through limiters in regions of strong gradients. Temporal derivatives use the implicit first-order Euler scheme, balancing stability and computational efficiency. Spatial gradients utilize the Gauss linear scheme, and convective terms the Gauss linearUpwind grad(U) scheme for enhanced stability. Pressure-velocity coupling is achieved via the PIMPLE algorithm [26], configured with appropriate correctors and convergence criteria to balance computational efficiency and solution accuracy. Complete details of all discretization schemes, solver settings, and algorithm parameters are provided in Tab. S.2 in Section S.2.1.

2.2.5. Time Stepping

The time step size Δt was determined based on two principal criteria: adequate resolution of the impeller rotation, and compliance with the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) condition:

To resolve the impeller motion, the time step was chosen such that the impeller advances by $\Delta\varphi = 1^\circ$ per time step, providing sufficient temporal resolution to capture transient flow features. In order to avoid aliasing effects, the time step size was further divided by 10 to enhance accuracy and thus the simulated motion of the impeller amounts to $\Delta\tilde{\varphi} = 0.1^\circ$ per time step. For the nominal shaft speed of 2880 min^{-1} , this results in $\Delta t = 5.79 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}$. For the lowest and highest shaft speeds considered (2070 min^{-1} and 3690 min^{-1}), the time steps are $8.05 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}$ and $4.52 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}$, respectively. Tab. S.3 in Section S.2.2 summarizes the time step sizes, total simulated physical times, and the corresponding number of impeller revolutions for all investigated operating conditions.

The second criterion for selecting the time step size is compliance with the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy condition, defined as $\text{CFL} = \frac{U\Delta t}{\Delta x}$, where Δx denotes the characteristic cell length. For transient simulations, it is generally recommended to maintain a CFL number below $\text{CFL} = 1$ to ensure numerical stability [27]. Since the PIMPLE algorithm is applied, it allows for stable and accurate operation at CFL numbers exceeding unity [26, 28, 29].

2.3. Computational Resources

The fully time-resolved CFD simulations required substantial computational resources in terms of CPU time, memory, and disk storage. To optimize disk usage, only time steps corresponding to the final 90° of the last impeller revolution were retained. Most field data were processed in situ, with essential quantities documented in log files for convergence monitoring and post-processing. Integral metrics, such as pressure head and hydraulic power, were evaluated over the entire simulation interval, while spatially resolved quantities (e.g., velocity and turbulent dissipation rate) were available exclusively for the stored time steps.

Simulations were performed on a high-performance computing (HPC) cluster utilizing 96 cores (2.6 GHz Intel Xeon Gold 6126, 93 GB RAM), with each job allocated 24 GB RAM. Parallelization was achieved via domain decomposition using the `simple` method, ensuring balanced subdomain sizes and assigning interface regions to the same subdomain.

2.4. Validation

2.4.1. Computational Quality Metrics

Simulation quality was assessed using six key metrics. These metrics ensure numerical reliability and accuracy. All validations reference the design operating point (10 L h^{-1} at 2880 min^{-1}) unless otherwise specified. Following these key metrics, a well formulated numerical model was established. However, each study underlies limitations, which may impact the results and their interpretation; see Section S.3 for a more detailed discussion.

- (i) Initial time steps occasionally exceeded the predefined limit of 50 PIMPLE iterations due to transient startup effects, but subsequent iterations reached the **residual thresholds** and typically converged within 5 to 15 cycles as the solution stabilized; see Fig. S.1.
- (ii) Convergence assessment was not limited to residuals; **physical quantities** such as total pressure and pump head were continuously monitored to ensure solution stability; see Fig. S.2. After an instable startup phase, these quantities stabilized with periodical behavior. Most of the simulations showed stable periodicity after approximately 0.5 impeller revolutions.
- (iii) In OpenFOAM, assessment of **mass conservation** cannot rely solely on the residual curves. Instead, the mass flow imbalances were quantified by analyzing global and cumulative continuity errors. Across all simulations, the maximum mass flow imbalance remains below 2.29×10^{-9} for the global error and below 4.14×10^{-6} for the cumulative error, respectively. The maximum values for both the global and cumulative errors occurred at the highest shaft speed of 3690 min^{-1} . However, global values of about 1×10^{-9} to 1×10^{-8} indicate excellent mass conservation throughout. Continuity errors for all operating points are listed in Tab. S.4.
- (iv) **The dimensionless wall distance** y^+ was systematically evaluated across all wall surfaces to verify sufficient boundary layer resolution. For each time step, spatially averaged y^+ values were computed and subsequently averaged over the final complete impeller revolution to yield $\overline{y^+}$. As presented in Tab. S.5, the principal surfaces associated with **IMPELLER**, **WALL**, and **WALL_MOVING** consistently exhibit mean $\overline{y^+}$ values below 5, thereby confirming full boundary layer resolution in accordance with the requirements of the $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model. In contrast, the **cyclicACMI** interface patches display elevated $\overline{y^+}$ values, particularly on the stationary sides, reaching up to approximately 32. Achieving lower y^+ values in these regions would necessitate a substantial increase in mesh density and overall computational cost. Given that these patches correspond to the breaker channel region, which is not critical to the primary flow dynamics, this compromise was considered acceptable within the scope of the present study. The dimensionless wall distance y^+ is summarized in Tab. S.5 as maximum values over all investigated conditions.
- (v) Across all simulations, the mean **CFL number** remained below unity, while the maximum CFL values ranged from approximately 6 to 8, as can be seen in Fig. S.3a. These values are well within the stable operating regime of the PIMPLE algorithm, ensuring both numerical stability and accurate resolution of transient flow phenomena within the pump.
- (vi) To assess the mesh **quality for resolving modeled turbulence**, particularly the turbulent dissipation rate ε , the ratio of the inertial turbulence length scale l_0 to the local mesh size Δ was evaluated. According to Wilcox [23], the inertial length scale is estimated as $l_0 \approx k^{1/2}/(\omega \cdot C_\mu)$. The local mesh size Δ is defined as the cube root of the cell volume. To ensure sufficient mesh resolution, a minimum ratio of $l_0/\Delta > 5$ was targeted throughout the domain, providing adequate spatial resolution for URANS simulations and reliable prediction of ε . Fig. S.3b illustrates the spatial distribution of the ratio l_0/Δ .

2.4.2. Validation Against Manufacturer Data

The numerical results were extensively validated against the manufacturer’s performance curve data. Fig. 2.5 repeats the head course of the pump for its design shaft speed of 2880 min^{-1} and shows two off-design shaft speeds (2070 min^{-1} and 3690 min^{-1}) applying affinity laws. It should be noted that the applicability of affinity laws is generally limited, as they were originally derived for centrifugal pumps; deviations may arise, particularly outside the nominal range. However, as discussed by Chen *et al.* [30], affinity laws can also be extended to sidechannel pumps. Since sidechannel pumps share operational similarities with peripheral pumps, validity of the affinity laws is also assumed for peripheral pumps, which is why affinity laws are taken for comparison. Affinity law-based extrapolations for varying shaft speeds are shown in gray. The circle markers of the black curve in Fig. 2.2 denote the operating points investigated by the manufacturer, which served as reference cases for the validation of the numerical results (see Fig. 2.5).

Figure 2.5.: Manufacturer performance curve of the pump under consideration and affinity laws for different speeds. The markers indicate the operating points investigated by the manufacturer.

The CFD simulation results are depicted in blue, green and red in Fig. 2.5. The computed head values were directly compared with both the manufacturer’s data and affinity law predictions. Since the affinity law approach yields flow rates that do not always coincide with the simulated points, linear interpolation was used between adjacent operating points to determine the corresponding flow rates. These interpolated values were then used to quantify deviations between the CFD results and affinity law estimates.

Comparison of CFD results with manufacturer data demonstrates excellent agreement across all operating points, including the design point. Relative deviations are approximately 5% except at the lowest part-load (1 L h^{-1}) and highest overload (80 L h^{-1}) conditions, where deviations reach approximately 8% to 9%. At the lower off-design shaft speed (2070 min^{-1}), deviations from linear interpolated points range from 6% to 13% against affinity laws. However, it should be noted that at this shaft speed, the simulations did not converge to a physically valid solution

for the highest overload point (80 L h^{-1}), as the pump likely operates in the reverse flow regime under these conditions. For the higher off-design speed (3690 min^{-1}), deviations remain below 2% at partial load and the design point, but increase to about 6% under overload, indicating possible performance curve instability. Similar trends are observed for other curves; however, detailed investigation of these instabilities is beyond the scope of this study.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Turbulent Dissipation Rate

3.1.1. Spatial Distribution

The spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ε was analyzed using coaxial slices at selected radial positions r_i , extracted from the CFD results and presented as unwrapped planar views following Reviol *et al.* [31]. For a detailed discussion, five radii were selected to unwrap: the hub radius ($r_{\text{Hub}} = r_0$), the mid-span radius ($r_{\text{Mid}} = r_4$), the tip radius ($r_{\text{Tip}} = r_8$), a radius within the sidechannel gap (r_9), and a radius near the shroud (r_{10}). These observation positions are shown together with all investigated radii in Fig. 3.1a and are summarized in Tab. S.6. For a better understanding, Fig. 3.1b also shows the angular observation position φ used in the unwrapped plots.

Figure 3.1.: Positions of observation at the pump.

Fig. 3.2 presents the turbulent dissipation rate ε for these five radii for the design operating point (10 L h^{-1} , 2880 min^{-1}), which are discussed in detail below. The characteristic distribution of ε is similar for all investigated operating points and is provided in Appendix S.4. Note that, because the k - ω SST model was utilized, ε is not solved directly but computed in post-processing from the turbulent kinetic energy k and the specific dissipation rate ω according to $\varepsilon = \beta^* k \omega$ with $\beta^* = 0.09$.

Figure 3.2.: Logarithmic spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ε at selected radii for the design operating point (10 L h^{-1} , 2880 min^{-1}). Main inlet at -45° ; secondary inlet: -90° ; outlet: 0° .

In Fig. 3.2, the color scale for ε is individually adjusted for each radius, with minimum and maximum values indicated below each plot. The scale is logarithmic to effectively represent the wide range of turbulent dissipation rates observed. The slices are unwrapped coaxial sections, with angular position φ along the ordinate and axial distance along the abscissa. The main inlet is located at $\varphi = -45$ deg, the secondary inlet at $\varphi = -90$ deg, and the outlet at $\varphi = 0$ deg, corresponding to Fig. 3.1b. Although the secondary inlet was not active in this study, its geometry influences the flow field. All slices span $\pm 180^\circ$, but their height varies due to the differences in radius. For better visualization, the angular positions, related to main inlet, secondary inlet, and outlet, are connected with dashed vertical lines. The figure demonstrates pronounced spatial variations in ε across all radii. At the hub, ε is relatively uniform, with a maximum of $\varepsilon = 6.39 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-3}$. The mid-span slice exhibits more intricate patterns, particularly within the impeller blade passages, where turbulent dissipation rates reach $\varepsilon = 9.33 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-3}$, corresponding to distinct circular flow structures, which form a tubular structure over the whole passage.

Fig. 3.3 presents a three-dimensional visualization of the tubular structures using the Q-criterion, a standard method for vortex identification in fluid flows. As defined in Eq. (3.1), the Q-criterion represents the second invariant of the velocity gradient tensor, distinguishing rotation-dominated regions (positive Q) from strain-dominated regions (negative Q). Here, Ω and S are the antisymmetric and symmetric parts, respectively, of the velocity-gradient tensor $\nabla \mathbf{U}$. Thus, vortical structures are effectively identified by positive Q values. The three-dimensional view at the mid-span radius of the figure shows the turbulent dissipation rate ε , with an iso-surface of the Q-criterion highlighting the tubular vortical structures within the impeller passages.

Figure 3.3.: 3D-visualization of the midspan, coloured by the turbulent dissipation rate ε with an iso-surface of the Q-criterion to visualize tubular structures [31].

$$Q = \frac{1}{2} (\|\Omega\|^2 - \|S\|^2) \quad (3.1)$$

The tubular structures are thus also observed at the tip slice, where the maximum values of ε amounts to $9.17 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-3}$. At this radius, the sidechannel is interrupted by the pump breaker, resulting in locally highest turbulent dissipation rates when fluid is passing through the narrow

breaker channel and reaches the suction side again. In contrast, the lowest values of ε are found close to this region, also associated with the breaker channel and caused by shadowing effects. Constrictions in the flow field are evident near both the main inlet and outlet, likely arising from fluid interactions as it exits the impeller, enters the sidechannel, and is redirected at the housing. At r_9 , within the sidechannel gap, these flow phenomena are even more pronounced, with the maximum turbulent dissipation rate reduced to $2.36 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-3}$. At the shroud, the flow field clearly reveals the flow structure, which transports fluid from impeller to sidechannel and back, as described above, with a maximum of $9.07 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-3}$. In the inlet region, turbulent dissipation rates remain low due to the well-formed flow in the inlet pipe.

In summary, the highest turbulent dissipation rates occur in the impeller region, especially within blade passages and near the sidechannel gap, while lower values are found at the hub and shroud. This distribution underscores the complex flow dynamics and localized turbulence generation within the pump.

3.1.2. Volumetric Quantification

The turbulent dissipation rate within the fluid domain is quantified by volume averaging, as defined in Eq. (3.2). Calculations are performed for both the entire fluid domain (Total) and the impeller region (Impeller), isolating the contribution of the impeller. The averaging domain volume is denoted by V_D , calculated from CFD as $V_{\text{Total}} = 5.94 \text{ mL}$ for the total fluid domain – which is slightly larger than the actual pump volume (5.2 mL) due to the extended inlet and outlet pipes in the numerical model – and $V_{\text{Impeller}} = 0.66 \text{ mL}$ for the impeller region. To account for flow unsteadiness, the volume-averaged turbulent dissipation rate $\bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{Vol}}$ is further averaged over the time span of a minimum angular interval of 90° , yielding $\langle \bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{Vol}} \rangle_t$.

$$\langle \bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{Vol}} \rangle_t = \frac{1}{\Delta t} \int_t \left(\frac{1}{V_D} \int_{V_D} \varepsilon \, dV \right) dt \quad (3.2)$$

The power consumption associated with turbulent dissipation rate, $\langle P_\varepsilon \rangle_t$, is calculated using Eq. (3.3), where ρ represents the fluid density and Δt is the observed time interval.

$$\langle P_\varepsilon \rangle_t = \frac{\rho}{\Delta t} \int_t \left(\int_{V_D} \varepsilon \, dV \right) dt \quad (3.3)$$

Both the volumetric and time averaged turbulent dissipation rate $\langle \bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{Vol}} \rangle_t$ and the associated power consumption $\langle P_\varepsilon \rangle_t$ are analyzed as functions of flow rate and shaft speed presented in Fig. 3.4. Results of the total fluid domain are shown as dashed lines, while impeller results are shown as solid lines. The lowest shaft speed of 2070 min^{-1} is represented in blue, the design shaft-speed of 2880 min^{-1} in green and the highest shaft speed of 3690 min^{-1} in red.

Fig. 3.4a demonstrates that the time- and volume-averaged turbulent dissipation rate increases markedly with rising shaft speed. The impeller region consistently exhibits significantly higher

Figure 3.4.: Time- and volume-averaged turbulent dissipation rate $\langle \bar{\varepsilon}_{Vol} \rangle_t$ and time-averaged power consumption $\langle P_\varepsilon \rangle_t$ versus flow rate and shaft speed for total and impeller regions, averaged over 90° .

rates than the total fluid domain, attributable to the inclusion of regions with relatively low dissipation – such as the inlet pipes, which are extended for the CFD model to mitigate inflow effects. For instance, at the design operating point (flow rate 10 L h^{-1} , shaft speed 2880 min^{-1}), the turbulent dissipation rate in the total domain is 567.98 W kg^{-1} , whereas the impeller region reaches $2653.60 \text{ W kg}^{-1}$. These absolute values should be considered as upper-bound estimates due to known limitations of eddy-viscosity turbulence models in complex three-dimensional flows. Additionally, increasing flow rate leads to a reduction in the turbulent dissipation rate, which is likely caused by the reduced residence time due to rising flow rates. Thus, the maximum averaged dissipation rate attains $6032.41 \text{ W kg}^{-1}$ in the impeller region at the highest shaft speed (3690 min^{-1}) and lowest flow rate (1 L h^{-1}). Comparison with literature values for RSM reveals that the peripheral pump achieves turbulent dissipation rates comparable to those of high-shear mixers typically used for micromixing. The peripheral pump was operated at Reynolds numbers of 3.11×10^4 , 4.32×10^4 and 5.54×10^4 for shaft speeds of 2070 min^{-1} , 2880 min^{-1} and 3690 min^{-1} , which are relatively low compared to those reported for mixers in the literature at similar dissipation rates, which reveals the potential of the peripheral pump for micromixing applications.

3.2. Kolmogorov Scales

3.2.1. Length Scale

To assess the suitability of the peripheral pump for micromixing, the Kolmogorov length scale, η , was calculated according to Eq. (3.4). Above this length scale species transport in the flow is dominated by convective processes. It represents the smallest turbulent structures in a turbulent flow and depends on the kinematic viscosity, ν , and the turbulent dissipation rate, ε . At this scale, viscous effects, convective mechanisms such as deformation and engulfment, and molecular diffusion become the primary drivers of mixing [32].

$$\eta = \left(\frac{\nu^3}{\varepsilon} \right)^{1/4} \quad (3.4)$$

(a) Flow rate 1 L h⁻¹, speed 2880 min⁻¹.

(b) Flow rate 10 L h⁻¹, speed 2880 min⁻¹.

(c) Flow rate 20 L h⁻¹, speed 2880 min⁻¹.

(d) Flow rate 40 L h⁻¹, speed 2880 min⁻¹.

(e) Flow rate 80 L h⁻¹, speed 2880 min⁻¹.

Figure 3.5.: Kolmogorov length scale η at various flow rates (1 L h⁻¹, 10 L h⁻¹, 20 L h⁻¹, 40 L h⁻¹ and 80 L h⁻¹) along the design curve (2880 min⁻¹). (i) High suitability for micromixing, (ii) threshold at 5 μ m, (iii) low suitability, (iv) unsuitable for micromixing as $\eta > 10 \mu$ m.

Regions with very small Kolmogorov length scales are highly favorable for micromixing, as the

resulting fine turbulent structures promote rapid diffusion and enable fast chemical reactions. In this study, $\eta < 5 \mu\text{m}$ is considered optimal for micromixing. For intermediate scales, $\eta = 5 \mu\text{m}$ to $10 \mu\text{m}$, mixing remains efficient and can still support fast reactions [32]. However, when $\eta > 10 \mu\text{m}$, the effectiveness for micromixing is significantly reduced, and the peripheral pump is deemed unsuitable for such applications. These thresholds are somewhat arbitrary but are informed by established literature, providing a clear basis for evaluating the flow field investigated in this study [32–37].

Figures 3.5 and 3.6 illustrate the Kolmogorov length scale η at various operating points for a representative time step. Fig. 3.5 shows η at different flow rates (1 L h^{-1} , 10 L h^{-1} , 20 L h^{-1} , 40 L h^{-1} and 80 L h^{-1}) for constant design shaft speed (2880 min^{-1}), while Fig. 3.6 presents η at different shaft speeds (2070 min^{-1} , 2880 min^{-1} and 3690 min^{-1}) but for constant design flow rate (10 L h^{-1}). The color scale, ranging from green to red, is consistently applied to all plots and covers the interval from $1 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}$ to $1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}$ ($0.1 \mu\text{m}$ to $10 \mu\text{m}$). The threshold for efficient micromixing, $\eta = 5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}$ ($5 \mu\text{m}$), is indicated on the color bar. All boundaries are represented as solid iso-lines within the plots. Regions shaded in green correspond to high micromixing suitability, whereas red regions indicate low or insufficient suitability, with black iso-lines delineating the boundary for effective micromixing at $\eta = 5 \mu\text{m}$. Note that the impeller position – and hence the observation plane within the impeller – varies between operating points due to the transient nature of the simulation.

Fig. 3.5 reveals that the Kolmogorov length scale is lowest within the blade passages and the sidechannel near the tip, while it increases towards the housing (region (iv)). The contour plots indicate an extended circular zone in the blade passages where η exceeds $5 \mu\text{m}$ (region (iii)), whereas values adjacent to the blades and near the hub remain below $5 \mu\text{m}$ (region (i)). The $5 \mu\text{m}$ iso-line is denoted by (ii). These patterns are attributed to the tubular flow structures formed by the characteristic exchange between impeller and sidechannel. Additionally, the breaker channel exhibits consistently low Kolmogorov length scales, generating a downstream region of reduced η . The spatial distribution of the Kolmogorov length scale remains largely unaffected by changes in flow rate. The observed patterns persist across all investigated flow rates at the constant shaft speed of 2880 min^{-1} .

In contrast to the largely negligible effect of flow rate, Fig. 3.6 reveals a pronounced dependence of the Kolmogorov length scale on shaft speed. This observation is consistent with the averaged energy dissipation rates in the impeller region, as shown in Fig. 3.4. An increase in the flow rate from 1 to 80 L h^{-1} leads to a decrease in the turbulent energy dissipation rate, ε , from 2900 W kg^{-1} to 1800 W kg^{-1} , corresponding to a reduction of 59%. In contrast, an increase in the impeller speed from 2070 min^{-1} to 3690 min^{-1} at a flow rate of 40 L h^{-1} results in an increase of ε from 800 to 5000 W kg^{-1} , representing a rise of 525%. The detailed view of the spatial distribution of the length scale η in Fig. 3.6 shows, that as shaft speed increases from $n = 2070 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (Fig. 3.6a) to $n = 3690 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (Fig. 3.6c), the region of high micromixing suitability (i) expands, particularly in the blade passages, while the area of low suitability (iii) contracts. Enhanced suitability is also observed within the sidechannel. Compared to the design shaft speed of $n = 2880 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (Fig. 3.6b), the wake induced by the breaker channel is less pronounced at lower shaft speed and more pronounced at higher shaft speed. Fig. 3.6c clearly demonstrates that optimal micromixing,

(a) Flow rate 10 L h^{-1} , speed 2070 min^{-1} .

(b) Flow rate 10 L h^{-1} , speed 2880 min^{-1} .

(c) Flow rate 10 L h^{-1} , speed 3690 min^{-1} .

Figure 3.6.: Kolmogorov length scale η at various shaft speeds (2070 min^{-1} , 2880 min^{-1} and 3690 min^{-1}) for constant flow rate (10 L h^{-1}). (i) High suitability for micromixing, (ii) threshold at $5 \mu\text{m}$, (iii) low suitability, (iv) unsuitable for micromixing as $\eta > 10 \mu\text{m}$.

as indicated by the Kolmogorov length scale η , is achieved at the highest shaft speed.

3.2.2. Time Scale

The Kolmogorov time scale τ_η , defined in Eq. (3.5), characterizes the turnover time of the smallest turbulent eddies and is utilized here to assess micromixing characteristics as it is closely linked to the micromixing time scale for fluids with Schmidt numbers lower than 4000 [38].

$$\tau_\eta = \sqrt{\nu/\varepsilon} \quad (3.5)$$

The instantaneous Kolmogorov time scale τ_η at various flow rates (1 L h^{-1} , 10 L h^{-1} , 20 L h^{-1} , 40 L h^{-1} and 80 L h^{-1}) for constant design shaft speed (2880 min^{-1}) is illustrated in Fig. 3.7. The scale spans from $1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}$ to $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}$ ($1 \mu\text{s}$ to $100 \mu\text{s}$). Iso-lines are drawn at $11 \mu\text{s}$, $50 \mu\text{s}$, and $100 \mu\text{s}$.

All plots in Fig. 3.7 demonstrate that the Kolmogorov time scale remains low throughout the

fluid domain, with most regions exhibiting $\tau_\eta < 1 \times 10^{-4}$ s. Consistent with Fig. 3.6, the blade passages display circular zones of reduced τ_η , while the sidechannel, particularly near the tip, also features low Kolmogorov time scales. The breaker channel is characterized by the lowest time scale values, resulting in a downstream region of reduced τ_η extending into the sidechannel. The spatial distribution of τ_η within the sidechannel is broader and less sharply defined, with extended areas of low values across the sidechannel gap. These patterns persist across all depicted flow rates and align with the observations for the Kolmogorov length scale η at these operating conditions. Thus, the Kolmogorov time scale τ_η is largely unaffected by changes in flow rate.

(a) Flow rate 1 L h^{-1} , speed 2880 min^{-1} .

(b) Flow rate 10 L h^{-1} , speed 2880 min^{-1} .

(c) Flow rate 20 L h^{-1} , speed 2880 min^{-1} .

(d) Flow rate 40 L h^{-1} , speed 2880 min^{-1} .

(e) Flow rate 80 L h^{-1} , speed 2880 min^{-1} .

Figure 3.7.: Kolmogorov time scale τ_η at various flow rates (1 L h^{-1} , 10 L h^{-1} , 20 L h^{-1} , 40 L h^{-1} and 80 L h^{-1}) along the design curve (2880 min^{-1}).

Figure 3.8.: Kolmogorov time scale τ_η at various shaft speeds (2070 min^{-1} , 2880 min^{-1} and 3690 min^{-1}) for constant flow rate (10 L h^{-1}).

Fig. 3.8 presents the Kolmogorov time scale τ_η at different shaft speeds (2070 min^{-1} , 2880 min^{-1} and 3690 min^{-1}) for the design flow rate (10 L h^{-1}). The spatial distribution of τ_η is strongly affected by shaft speed, with increasing speed resulting in lower time scales throughout the domain. At the lowest shaft speed (Fig. 3.8a), relatively elevated values of τ_η are observed in the sidechannel and within certain regions of the blade passages, although these remain low in absolute terms. As the shaft speed increases to $n = 2880 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (Fig. 3.8b), the Kolmogorov time scale decreases, particularly within the sidechannel. At the highest shaft speed ($n = 3690 \text{ min}^{-1}$, Fig. 3.8c), τ_η is further reduced, resulting in uniformly low time scales below $50 \mu\text{s}$ across the entire fluid domain.

This observed behavior is consistent with that reported for the Kolmogorov length scale. There, the dependence of η on the flow rate was similarly weak, whereas the dependence on the impeller speed was more pronounced. This matches the expected behavior, as both the Kolmogorov length scale and the corresponding time scale scale with the inverse fourth root and the inverse square root of the energy dissipation rate, ε , respectively.

The Kolmogorov time scale τ_η serves as a critical indicator of mixing performance. Across all investigated operating points, τ_η remains below $100 \mu\text{s}$ throughout extensive regions of the fluid domain, demonstrating the peripheral pump's strong suitability for micromixing applications. This conclusion is further supported by the consistently low Kolmogorov length scale η observed

in key regions.

Since the Kolmogorov time scale, τ_η , is directly linked to the micromixing time scale, t_{mix} , via $t_{\text{mix}} = 17.3\tau_\eta$, the estimated micromixing time for Kolmogorov time scales on the order of $\tau_\eta \approx 100 \mu\text{s}$ is approximately 10^{-3} s. This value is in good agreement with experimentally obtained micromixing times for the same peripheral pump model reported by Ashrafmansouri *et al.* [4], who measured mixing times ranging from 10^{-4} s to 10^{-2} s. This comparison supports the validity of the present CFD study.

3.3. Mixing Efficiency

To assess the mixing efficiency of the peripheral pump, the hydraulic efficiency $\eta_{\text{hydraulic}}$, defined as $\eta_{\text{hydraulic}} = P_{\text{hydraulic}}/P_{\text{input}}$, is first determined based on CFD results. The input power P_{input} is computed from the shaft torque due to viscous and pressure forces. The hydraulic power associated with the fluid pressure rise is $P_{\text{hydraulic}} = \rho g H \dot{V}$, where H denotes the pump head of the peripheral pump. Fig. 3.9 presents the computed input power P_{input} (Fig. 3.9a) and the resulting hydraulic efficiency $\eta_{\text{hydraulic}}$ (Fig. 3.9b) as functions of flow rate for the three investigated shaft speeds.

Figure 3.9.: CFD calculated power performance of the peripheral pump: (a) Power input $P_{\text{hydraulic}}$ and (b) hydraulic efficiency $\eta_{\text{hydraulic}}$ versus flow rate for three shaft speeds (2070 min^{-1} , 2880 min^{-1} and 3690 min^{-1}).

Fig. 3.9a shows that the input power P_{input} near the shut-off head is lowest at $n = 2070 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (blue squares), about 2.4 W. Increasing the shaft speed to the design value $n = 2880 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (green circles) raises P_{input} to roughly 6.7 W, and further increasing the speed to $n = 3690 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (red triangles) increases it to about 14.4 W. For all shaft speeds, P_{input} decreases with increasing flow rate, although shaft speed remains the dominant influence. Fig. 3.9b indicates that the hydraulic efficiency $\eta_{\text{hydraulic}}$ is largely independent of shaft speed. Hydraulic efficiency increases with flow rate up to approximately 40 L h^{-1} . At higher flow rates the efficiency appears to plateau at roughly 7% to 9%, which is close to the hydraulic efficiency of the pump of 10% reported by Ashrafmansouri *et al.* [4]. Determining a clear peak would require detailed data beyond 40 L h^{-1} . Note that for the lowest shaft speed no data are available at the overload flow rate of 80 L h^{-1} .

because the pump could not be operated stably under those conditions. It is also notably, that the manufacturer's design operating point of 10 L h^{-1} is not the point of maximum hydraulic efficiency.

Following Kresta *et al.* [7], the mixing efficiency η_{mix} is defined as the power associated with turbulent dissipation rate, here using the time-averaged value $\langle P_\varepsilon \rangle_t$, to the power effort, here using the hydraulic power input P_{input} , as shown in Eq. (3.6).

$$\eta_{\text{mix}} = \frac{\langle P_\varepsilon \rangle_t}{P_{\text{input}}} \quad (3.6)$$

Fig. 3.10 presents the mixing efficiency η_{mix} as a function of flow rate. Since the time-averaged power consumption $\langle P_\varepsilon \rangle_t$ is computed in Fig. 3.4 for both the impeller region and the total fluid domain, the mixing efficiency η_{mix} is also shown for both regions. Solid coloured lines denote values computed for the impeller region, while coloured dashed lines denote values for the total fluid domain. Shaft speeds are indicated by markers: $n = 2070 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (blue squares), $n = 2880 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (green circles), and $n = 3690 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (red triangles). For reference, the hydraulic efficiency is plotted as gray dashed lines using the same markers.

In contrast to both the time- and volume-averaged turbulent dissipation rate presented in Fig. 3.4 and input power presented in Fig. 3.9a, the mixing efficiency η_{mix} exhibits the opposite behaviour: the influence of shaft speed is less pronounced, while flow rate has a relatively stronger effect. Nevertheless, the impact of flow rate remains moderate, being more evident at lower flow rates and diminishing at higher flow rates.

Compared to the hydraulic efficiency $\eta_{\text{hydraulic}}$, the mixing efficiency η_{mix} in the impeller region is substantially higher at low flow rates and approximately twice as high at large flow rates. Considering the total fluid domain, mixing efficiency η_{mix} is roughly five times greater than the hydraulic efficiency $\eta_{\text{hydraulic}}$.

Figure 3.10.: Mixing efficiency η_{mix} as a function of flow rate for the three shaft speeds under investigation (2070 min^{-1} , 2880 min^{-1} and 3690 min^{-1}), shown for both the impeller region (coloured solid lines) and the total fluid domain (coloured dashed lines) in comparison to the hydraulic efficiency (gray dashed lines), averaged over time span corresponding to 90° .

This outcome is consistent with the energetic balance: the power associated with turbulent dissipation is provided by the portion of the input power that cannot be converted into hydraulic power. Hence, increased turbulent dissipation corresponds to reduced hydraulic efficiency. In this context, operating conditions that exhibit lower hydraulic efficiency are more likely to produce higher mixing efficiency, underscoring the suitability of peripheral pumps for micromixing applications.

4. Conclusion and outlook

This study provides a comprehensive quantitative evaluation of peripheral pumps for micromixing applications. The central research question of how the fluid mechanics – specifically the flow topology in general and particularly the turbulent dissipation within the pump – enables peripheral pumps to be suitable for micromixing can be answered through detailed, spatially and temporally resolved results.

The investigated HMR-020 peripheral pump demonstrates exceptional micromixing capability, achieving volume- and time-averaged turbulent dissipation rates up to 6032 W kg^{-1} in the impeller region, which are comparable to dedicated rotor-stator mixers but attained at moderate Reynolds numbers ($Re = 3.1 \times 10^4$ to 5.5×10^4). Distinct flow features – particularly the interaction between impeller and sidechannel, as well as the breaker channel and its wake – are identified as primary contributors to elevated micromixing.

A Kolmogorov length scale analysis was performed, revealing extensive regions with $\eta < 5 \mu\text{m}$, which are optimal for micromixing. These regions depend strongly on shaft speed but show little dependence on flow rate. In particular, the blade passages, breaker channel, and its wake exhibit very small Kolmogorov length scales. Similar findings were observed for the Kolmogorov time scale, another key parameter for micromixing. Values of τ_η below 0.1 ms were found in large parts of the peripheral pump, reaching approximately $1 \mu\text{s}$ in the blade passages, confirming optimal conditions for rapid molecular-level mixing. In general, the Kolmogorov time scales show the same patterns and dependencies as the Kolmogorov length scales, but reach a broader range of low values in the sidechannel.

As a final assessment of the suitability of peripheral pumps for micromixing, the mixing efficiency η_{mix} was calculated, based on metrics from the literature on stirred tank reactors. This enables a direct comparison of the mixing efficiency between different mixers. The mixing efficiency of the investigated peripheral pump ranges up to 55% at low flow rates. Notably, the mixing efficiency exhibits minimal sensitivity to shaft speed, which contrasts sharply with the dependencies observed for other key parameters in this study. This favorable mixing efficiency effectively compensates for the inherently moderate hydraulic efficiency characteristic of peripheral pump designs.

Compared to established mixing technologies, peripheral pumps offer unique advantages. They provide simultaneous pumping and mixing, eliminating the need for separate transport systems. Their wide operating range enables process flexibility unmatched by static mixers, their robust design suits harsh industrial environments better than delicate micromixers, and moderate Reynolds numbers reduce energy requirements compared to high-speed rotor-stator mixers.

This study establishes peripheral pumps as promising candidates for micromixing, with performance rivaling dedicated high-shear mixers. The potential of peripheral pumps is high, but further research is needed to validate calculation models, understand flow dynamics, and finally optimize designs of peripheral pumps to fully exploit the potential of peripheral pumps for micromixing applications:

- *Experimental validation of numerical results.* To evaluate and improve the understanding of the flow topology, causing high turbulent dissipation rates, detailed experimental studies are required. High-resolution Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) or Large Eddy PIV (LE-PIV) measurements would provide velocity field data for direct comparison with CFD results, which also enable the derivation of turbulence characteristics for comparison and validation.
- *Advanced turbulence modeling.* URANS simulations tend to overestimate turbulent dissipation rates. LES can provide more accurate results. Combining LES CFD simulations with LE-PIV experiments would yield a comprehensive understanding of the flow dynamics and turbulence characteristics.
- *Optimization of pump design for micromixing.* The current study is focussed on a single pump model and a limited set of operating conditions. To identify optimal design for micromixing, a broader range of geometrical and operational parameters should be investigated. The influence of the secondary inlet is still unknown and should be studied in detail. Since the breaker channel and its wake reveal high turbulent dissipation rates and small Kolmogorov scales close to the housing, further investigations should focus on this area. Positioning the secondary inlet in these regions could be beneficial for micromixing.
- *Scale-up studies.* Industrial applications require scaling laws for turbulent dissipation rates and Kolmogorov scales. Systematic studies on pumps of different sizes and capacities will help establish these relationships.
- *Extension to multiphase and reactive flows.* Many micromixing applications involve multiphase systems or chemical reactions. Extending both, experimental investigations and CFD simulations to multiphase and reactive flows will broaden the applicability of peripheral pumps in chemical and pharmaceutical processes.

Acknowledgements

Funding: This work was supported by the Berdelle-Hilge Stiftung, Germany. All simulations were performed on the high-performance computing cluster of the Allianz für Hochleistungsrechnen Rheinland-Pfalz (AHRP), <https://www.ahrp.info>.

References

- [1] J. R. Bourne, “Mixing and the selectivity of chemical reactions,” *Organic Process Research & Development*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 471–508, 2003. DOI: 10.1021/op020074q.
- [2] S. Huang *et al.*, “Design and development of a new static mixing bioreactor for enzymatic bioprocess: Application in biodiesel production,” *Renewable Energy*, vol. 197, pp. 922–931, 2022. DOI: 10.1016/j.renene.2022.08.003.
- [3] G. S. Reddy, N. S. Reddy, K. Manudhane, M. V. R. Krishna, K. J. S. Ramachandra, and S. Gangula, “Application of continuous flow micromixing reactor technology for synthesis of benzimidazole drugs,” *Organic Process Research & Development*, vol. 17, no. 10, pp. 1272–1276, 2013. DOI: 10.1021/op300325f.
- [4] S.-S. Ashrafmansouri, A. Kraus, S. Osterroth, and E. von Harbou, “Investigation of micro- and mesomixing in a reaction mixing pump,” *International Journal of Energy Research*, vol. 525, no. 1, p. 169785, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.cej.2025.169785.
- [5] A. N. Manzano Martínez, K. M. van Eeten, J. C. Schouten, and J. van der Schaaf, “Micromixing in a rotor-stator spinning disc reactor,” *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 56, no. 45, pp. 13454–13460, 2017. DOI: 10.1021/acs.iecr.7b01324.
- [6] A. N. Manzano Martínez, R. Jansen, K. Walker, M. Assirelli, and J. van der Schaaf, “Experimental and modeling study on meso- and micromixing in the rotor-stator spinning disk reactor,” *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, vol. 173, pp. 279–288, 2021. DOI: 10.1016/j.cherd.2021.07.012.
- [7] S. M. Kresta and P. E. Wood, “Prediction of the three-dimensional turbulent flow in stirred tanks,” *AIChE Journal*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 448–460, 1991. DOI: 10.1002/aic.690370314.
- [8] H. Hartmann, J. J. Derksen, C. Montavon, J. Pearson, I. S. Hamill, and H. van den Akker, “Assessment of large eddy and RANS stirred tank simulations by means of LDA,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 59, no. 12, pp. 2419–2432, 2004. DOI: 10.1016/j.ces.2004.01.065.
- [9] F. Azizi, W. Abou-Hweij, N. Lebaz, and N. Sheibat-Othman, “A numerical evaluation of flows through an SMX-Plus mixer,” *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, vol. 178, pp. 382–394, 2022. DOI: 10.1016/j.cherd.2021.12.030.
- [10] J. Albertazzi, V. Busini, and R. Rota, “Comparison through a CFD approach of static mixers in an emulsification process,” *International Journal of Thermofluids*, vol. 22, p. 100708, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijft.2024.100708.

- [11] H. Meng, T. Meng, Y. Yu, Z. Wang, and J. Wu, “Experimental and numerical investigation of turbulent flow and heat transfer characteristics in the Komax static mixer,” *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, vol. 194, p. 123 006, 2022. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2022.123006.
- [12] E. Chabanon, N. Sheibat-Othman, O. Mdere, J. P. Valour, S. Urbaniak, and F. Puel, “Drop size distribution monitoring of oil-in-water emulsions in SMX+ static mixers: Effect of operating and geometrical conditions,” *International Journal of Multiphase Flow*, vol. 92, pp. 61–69, 2017. DOI: 10.1016/J.IJMULTIPHASEFLOW.2017.03.001.
- [13] K. He *et al.*, “Numerical simulation of liquid–liquid dispersion characteristics in screen-type static mixers by two simplified zero-dimensional models,” *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 62, no. 20, pp. 8085–8097, 2023. DOI: 10.1021/acs.iecr.3c00816.
- [14] C. Espinoza, F. Alberini, O. Mihailova, A. J. Kowalski, and M. Simmons, “Flow, turbulence and potential droplet break up mechanisms in an in-line Silverson 150/250 high shear mixer,” *Chemical Engineering Science: X*, vol. 6, p. 100 055, 2020. DOI: 10.1016/j.cesx.2020.100055.
- [15] B. A. Minnick, E. E. Janz, and R. V. Calabrese, “CFD simulation of an axial discharge rotor-stator mixer: LES versus RANS predictions,” *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, vol. 198, pp. 413–430, 2023. DOI: 10.1016/j.cherd.2023.08.047.
- [16] M. P. Vasilev and R. Abiev, “Intensity and efficiency of droplet dispersion: Pulsating flow type apparatus vs. static mixers,” *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, vol. 137, pp. 329–349, 2018. DOI: 10.1016/J.CHERD.2018.07.029.
- [17] J. B. You *et al.*, “PDMS-based turbulent microfluidic mixer,” *Lab on a chip*, vol. 15, no. 7, pp. 1727–1735, 2015. DOI: 10.1039/c51c00070j.
- [18] P. Guichardon and L. Falk, “Characterisation of micromixing efficiency by the iodide-iodate reaction system. Part I: experimental procedure,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 55, no. 19, pp. 4233–4243, 2000. DOI: 10.1016/S0009-2509(00)00068-3.
- [19] L. Falk and J. M. Commenge, “Performance comparison of micromixers,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 65, no. 1, pp. 405–411, 2010. DOI: 10.1016/j.ces.2009.05.045.
- [20] D. Appiah, F. Zhang, S. Yuan, and M. K. Osman, “Effects of the geometrical conditions on the performance of a side channel pump: A review,” *International Journal of Energy Research*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 416–428, 2018. DOI: 10.1002/er.3803.
- [21] F. Zhang, D. Appiah, K. Chen, S. Yuan, K. A. Adu-Poku, and L. Zhu, “Investigation on the flow behavior of side channel pumps based on vortex identification,” *Chinese Journal of Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 34, no. 1, 2021. DOI: 10.1186/s10033-021-00649-1.
- [22] K. Chen *et al.*, “Effect of blade tip cutting angle on energy conversion mechanism of side channel pumps,” *Physics of Fluids*, vol. 34, no. 2, 2022. DOI: 10.1063/5.0082671.
- [23] D. C. Wilcox, *Turbulence modeling for CFD*, Third edition. La Cañada, California: DCW Industries, 2006, ISBN: 978-1-928729-08-2.

- [24] F. R. Menter, “Two-equation eddy-viscosity turbulence models for engineering applications,” *AIAA Journal*, vol. 32, no. 8, pp. 1598–1605, 1994. DOI: 10.2514/3.12149.
- [25] *VDI-Wärmeatlas: Berechnungsunterlagen für Druckverlust, Wärme- und Stoffübergang*, 10., bearb. und erw. Aufl. Berlin: Springer, 2006, ISBN: 3-540-25504-4.
- [26] S. Zheng, Z. J. Zhai, Y. Wang, Y. Xue, L. Duanmu, and W. Liu, “Evaluation and comparison of various fast fluid dynamics modeling methods for predicting airflow around buildings,” *Building Simulation*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 1083–1095, 2022. DOI: 10.1007/s12273-021-0860-1.
- [27] J. H. Ferziger, M. Perić, and R. L. Street, *Computational methods for fluid dynamics*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020, ISBN: 978-3-319-99691-2. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-99693-6.
- [28] J. Li, Y. Liao, D. Lucas, and P. Zhou, “Stability analysis of discrete population balance model for bubble growth and shrinkage,” *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Fluids*, vol. 93, no. 12, pp. 3338–3363, 2021. DOI: 10.1002/flid.5036.
- [29] N. N. Zadeh and R. Paoli, “Numerical experiments of subsonic jet flow simulations using RANS with OpenFOAM,” *Open Journal of Fluid Dynamics*, vol. 12, no. 02, pp. 230–247, 2022. DOI: 10.4236/ojfd.2022.122011.
- [30] K. Chen, F. Zhang, R. Liu, K. A. Adu-Pokua, S. Yuan, and Q. Hong, “Experimental and numerical evaluation of affinity law of single-stage and multistage side channel pumps at variable rotating speeds,” *Journal of Fluids Engineering*, vol. 145, no. 10, 2023. DOI: 10.1115/1.4062648.
- [31] T. Reviol, A. Kraus, S.-S. Ashrafmansouri, and E. von Harbou, *Numerical analysis of the flow topology and the turbulent dissipation rate in a peripheral pump*, 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17157481.
- [32] J. Baldyga and J. R. Bourne, “A fluid mechanical approach to turbulent mixing and chemical reaction part II micromixing in the light of turbulence theory,” *Chemical Engineering Communications*, vol. 28, no. 4-6, pp. 243–258, 1984. DOI: 10.1080/00986448408940136.
- [33] B. K. Johnson and R. K. Prud’homme, “Chemical processing and micromixing in confined impinging jets,” *AIChE Journal*, vol. 49, no. 9, pp. 2264–2282, 2003. DOI: 10.1002/aic.690490905.
- [34] D. Iurashev *et al.*, “Scaling strategy for cell and gene therapy bioreactors based on turbulent parameters,” *Biotechnology journal*, vol. 19, no. 1, e2300235, 2024. DOI: 10.1002/biot.202300235.
- [35] R. J. Demyanovich, “Experimental study and turbulence dissipative scale modelling of the rapid micromixing of impinging thin sheets of liquids,” *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, vol. 206, pp. 347–366, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.cherd.2024.04.060.
- [36] B. G. Lakatos, “The generalized coalescence/redispersion micromixing model. A multiscale approach,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 122, pp. 161–172, 2015. DOI: 10.1016/j.ces.2014.09.005.

-
- [37] J. Baldyga and J. R. Bourne, “Micromixing in inhomogeneous turbulence,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 107–112, 1988. DOI: 10.1016/0009-2509(88)87131-8.
- [38] J. Baldyga and J. R. Bourne, “Simplification of micromixing calculations: I. Derivation and application of new model,” *The Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 83–92, 1989. DOI: 10.1016/0300-9467(89)85002-6.

Nomenclature

Latin letters

b	Impeller width	m
C_μ	Turbulence model constant	-
D	Pipe diameter	m
g	Gravitational acceleration	m/s ²
H	Pump head	m
I	Turbulence intensity	-
k	Turbulent kinetic energy	m ² /s ²
l	Turbulence length scale	m
l_0	Integral length scale	m
n	Shaft speed	min ⁻¹
$\langle P_\varepsilon \rangle_t$	Time-averaged Power consumption based on Dissipation	W
$P_{\text{hydraulic}}$	Hydraulic power	W
P_{input}	Mechanical power input	W
Q	Q-criterion for vortex identification	s ⁻²
r	Radius	m
Re	Impeller Reynolds number $Re_{\text{Imp}} = n \cdot (2r_{\text{Tip}})^2 / \nu$	-
S	Strain rate tensor	s ⁻¹
t	Time	s
U	Velocity	m s ⁻¹
\mathbf{U}	Velocity vector	m s ⁻¹
U_∞	Mean inlet velocity	m s ⁻¹
V	Volume	m ³
V_{domain}	Domain volume	m ³
\dot{V}	Volumetric flow rate	L h ⁻¹
y^+	Dimensionless wall distance	-
$\overline{y^+}$	Averaged dimensionless wall distance	-

Greek letters

β^*	SST turbulence model constant	-
Δ	Cube root of the cell volume	m
Δt	Time step	s
Δx	Spatial step	m
$\Delta\varphi$	Impeller motion per time step for chosen rotation speed	°

continued ...

... continued

$\Delta\tilde{\varphi}$	Simulated impeller motion per time step avoiding Aliasing	°
ε	Turbulent dissipation rate	m^2/s^3
$\langle\tilde{\varepsilon}_{\text{Vol}}\rangle_t$	Time- and volume-averaged turbulent dissipation rate	m^2/s^3
η	Kolmogorov length scale	m
$\eta_{\text{hydraulic}}$	hydraulic efficiency	-
η_{mix}	Mixing efficiency	-
ν	Kinematic viscosity	m^2s^{-1}
ν_t	Turbulent viscosity	m^2s^{-1}
ρ	Fluid density	kgm^{-3}
τ_η	Kolmogorov time scale	s
φ	Angle, Observation angle	°
ω	Specific dissipation rate	s^{-1}
Ω	Vorticity tensor	s^{-1}

Subscripts

Hub	Parameter related to the hub
i	Index
Imp	Impeller related
Impeller	Impeller fluid domain
Mid	Parameter related to the Midspan
mix	Mixing related
Shroud	Parameter related to the shroud
t	time averaged
Tip	Parameter related to the tip
Total	Total fluid domain
vol	volume averaged

Abbreviations

AMI	Arbitrary Mesh Interface
ACMI	Arbitrary Coupled Mesh Interface
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CFL	Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy Number
Exp.	Experimental
HPC	High Performance Computing
LES	Large Eddy Simulation
PIMPLE	Pressure-Velocity Coupling Algorithm, Merge of PISO and SIMPLE
PISO	Pressure-Implicit with Splitting of Operators
PIV	Particle Image Velocimetry
RANS	Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes Equations
RSM	Rotor Stator Mixer
SIMPLE	Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure-Linked Equations

continued ...

... continued

SM	Static Mixer
SST	Shear Stress Transport
URANS	Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes Equations

Note if a variable has no unit this is indicated by -, if no specification is made the unit of the variable can change.

S. Supplementary Information

S.1. Details Pump Under Consideration

Table S.1.: Main geometric dimensions of the peripheral pump.

	Description	Symbol	Value
impeller	hub radius	$r_{\text{Imp,Hub}}$	10.5 mm
	midspan radius	$r_{\text{Imp,Mid}}$	12.75 mm
	tip radius	$r_{\text{Imp,Tip}}$	15 mm
	blade width	b_{Imp}	10 mm
sidechannel	inner radius	$r_{\text{SC,in}}$	10.5 mm
	outer radius	$r_{\text{SC,out}}$	16.5 mm
	total width	b_{SC}	13.72 mm
	operating angle	φ_{SC}	315°
breaker	gap lateral	$s_{\text{B,lat}}$	0.15 mm
	outer radius	$r_{\text{B,out}}$	16.5 mm
	angle	φ_{B}	45°

S.2. Details Numerical Setup

S.2.1. Numerical Methods

Table S.2.: Detailed numerical methods and solver settings employed in the CFD simulations.

Category	Parameter	Setting/Value
Fluid Properties	Density	998.21 kg m ⁻³
	Kinematic viscosity	1.003 × 10 ⁻⁶ m ² /s
	Temperature	293.15 K
	Compressibility	Incompressible
	Thermal treatment	Isothermal
	Rheology	Newtonian
Temporal Discretization	Time scheme	Euler
	Angular resolution	0.1° per time step

continued ...

... continued

Category	Parameter	Setting/Value
Spatial Discretization	Gradient scheme	Gauss linear
	Velocity gradients	Gauss linear (cell-limited)
	Convective terms	Gauss linearUpwind grad(U)
	Turbulence transport	Gauss upwind
	Viscous terms	Gauss linear
	Laplacian terms	Gauss linear limited corrected 0.33
	Interpolation	linear
	Surface-normal gradients	limited corrected 0.33
Linear System Solver	Pressure correction	GAMG
	Pressure smoother	DICGaussSeidel
	Pressure tolerance	1×10^{-2} (correction), 1×10^{-6} (field)
	Pressure max. iterations	50
	Velocity/turbulence solver	smoothSolver
	Velocity/turbulence smoother	symGaussSeidel
PIMPLE	Algorithm type	PIMPLE
	Outer correctors	50
	Correctors	2
	Non-orthogonal correctors	4
	Velocity residual criterion	1×10^{-5}
	Pressure residual criterion	5×10^{-4}
	Initial relaxation	0.2
	Final relaxation	0.8
Gradient caching	Velocity field	
Convergence Control	Velocity tolerance	1×10^{-6}
	Turbulence tolerance	1×10^{-6}
	Relative tolerance	0.1
	Relative tolerance (final)	0
Special Methods	Wall distance computation	meshWave
	Near-wall modeling	Fully resolved boundary layer
	Stability enhancement	Limiters in gradient regions

S.2.2. Time Stepping

Table S.3.: Time step sizes, total simulated times, and number of impeller revolutions for the investigated shaft speeds.

Flow rate		1 L h ⁻¹		10 L h ⁻¹		20 L h ⁻¹		40 L h ⁻¹		80 L h ⁻¹	
Shaft speed	Δt	T	N	T	N	T	N	T	N	T	N
min ⁻¹	10 ⁻⁶ s	10 ⁻² s		10 ⁻² s		10 ⁻² s		10 ⁻² s		10 ⁻² s	
2070	8.05	6.72	3.0	7.66	3.4	7.38	3.3	7.21	3.2	6.99	3.1
2880	5.79	5.17	2.5	3.46	1.7	3.81	1.8	4.68	2.2	3.50	1.7
3690	4.52	6.29	3.9	5.69	3.5	5.32	3.3	4.88	3.0	4.88	3.0

S.3. Details Numerical Validation

S.3.1. Study Limitations

A comprehensive mesh independence study is a standard requirement for rigorous CFD analysis to ensure the reliability of numerical results. However, in this work, the extremely high computational cost of fully time-resolved simulations of the turbulent dissipation rate ε made a systematic mesh refinement study infeasible. Each operating point required approximately two weeks of wall-clock time on a high-performance computing cluster, precluding a full parametric investigation within available resources. To address this limitation, mesh quality and solution fidelity were ensured through several measures: a fully hexahedral mesh was used, boundary layers were resolved with $\overline{y^+} < 5$, and turbulence was captured with $l_0/\Delta > 5$.

The simulation procedure was started, with initial runs at the design point validated against manufacturer data. Integral quantities converged rapidly, and numerical results closely matched experimental measurements without empirical adjustments, supporting the adequacy of the chosen mesh and numerical setup. Owing to the iteratively developed simulation methodology, investigations of the manufacturer's data were limited to 1.5 to 2 impeller revolutions per operating point, although 3.5 to 5 revolutions would be preferable for improved statistics, as performed for off-design shaft speeds. Due to resource constraints, extending the design curve was not pursued, as the CFD results already showed high agreement with manufacturer data.

An additional limitation concerns the turbulence modeling approach. Two-equation models based on the eddy-viscosity hypothesis, such as $k-\omega$ SST, are known to overpredict turbulent dissipation rates compared to LES and experimental measurements, particularly in complex three-dimensional flows with strong recirculation and anisotropic turbulence [15, 23]. This stems from the isotropic eddy-viscosity assumption, which cannot fully capture complex turbulent transport mechanisms. Consequently, absolute dissipation values should be interpreted as upper-bound estimates, while relative trends and operational dependencies remain reliable.

While these limitations – mesh independence, limited temporal averaging, and turbulence modeling constraints – remain to be addressed in future work, the present results are substantiated

by robust validation and high numerical quality. The excellent agreement with experimental data, despite the complexity of the flow, attests to the reliability of the adopted approach and the careful implementation of best practices in meshing and simulation.

S.3.2. Convergence Behavior

Figure S.1.: Residuals of all transport equations for the design operating point (10 L h^{-1} at 2880 min^{-1}) and continuity over time for the same operating point.

Figure S.2.: Total pressure at inlet and outlet and head for the design operating point (10 L h^{-1} at 2880 min^{-1}) and continuity over time.

Table S.4.: Mass flow rates for all investigated flow rates and shaft speeds. Time averaging was performed over all time steps.

Flow rate	1 L h^{-1}		10 L h^{-1}		20 L h^{-1}		40 L h^{-1}		80 L h^{-1}	
Shaft speed min^{-1}	glob.	cum.	glob.	cum.	glob.	cum.	glob.	cum.	glob.	cum.
	10^{-9}	10^{-6}	10^{-9}	10^{-6}	10^{-9}	10^{-6}	10^{-9}	10^{-6}	10^{-9}	10^{-6}
2070	1.51	1.29	1.60	2.07	1.14	2.22	1.58	1.95	1.63	1.04
2880	1.55	2.09	1.84	1.43	1.64	1.66	1.61	2.38	1.47	1.49
3690	2.29	3.96	1.63	4.14	1.69	3.98	2.13	3.77	2.15	3.43

S.3.3. Quality of Spatial and Temporal Resolution

Table S.5.: Maximum values of spatially and temporally averaged y^+ values for all investigated flow rates, shaft speeds, and surface patches. Time averaging was performed over one full impeller revolution.

Patch	$\overline{y^+}$
IMPELLER	4.44
WALL	4.85
WALL_MOVING	4.81
ACMI_IMPELLER_SIDECHANNEL_HOUSING_MOV	5.54
ACMI_IMPELLER_SIDECHANNEL_HOUSING_STAT	31.54
ACMI_IMPELLER_SIDECHANNEL_MOTOR_MOV	5.62
ACMI_IMPELLER_SIDECHANNEL_MOTOR_STAT	32.03

(a) CFL number distribution.

(b) Distribution of l_0/Δ .

Figure S.3.: CFL number and distribution of the ratio l_0/Δ for the design operating point (10 L h^{-1} at 2880 min^{-1}).

S.3.4. Preliminary Studies

Preliminary studies were performed to assess turbulence model selection and temporal resolution. Both $k-\epsilon$ and $k-\omega$ SST models were tested; the $k-\omega$ SST model showed better agreement with manufacturer data, especially for pump head prediction. Temporal resolution was validated by ensuring the time step resolved impeller rotation (0.1° per step) and maintained stable CFL numbers (mean < 1 , max 6 to 8), confirming suitability for transient flow simulation.

S.4. Details Results and Discussion

Figure S.4.: Logarithmic spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ε at selected radii for $1 L h^{-1}$ at $2070 min^{-1}$.

Figure S.5.: Logarithmic spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ϵ at selected radii for $5 L h^{-1}$ at $2070 min^{-1}$.

Figure S.6.: Logarithmic spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ε at selected radii for $10 L h^{-1}$ at $2070 min^{-1}$.

Figure S.7.: Logarithmic spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ϵ at selected radii for $20 L h^{-1}$ at $2070 min^{-1}$.

Figure S.8.: Logarithmic spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ϵ at selected radii for $40 L h^{-1}$ at $2070 min^{-1}$.

Figure S.9.: Logarithmic spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ϵ at selected radii for $80 L h^{-1}$ at $2070 min^{-1}$.

Figure S.10.: Logarithmic spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ϵ at selected radii for $1 L h^{-1}$ at $2880 min^{-1}$.

Figure S.11.: Logarithmic spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ϵ at selected radii for $20 L h^{-1}$ at $2880 min^{-1}$.

Figure S.12.: Logarithmic spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ϵ at selected radii for $40 L h^{-1}$ at $2880 min^{-1}$.

Figure S.13.: Logarithmic spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ϵ at selected radii for $80 L h^{-1}$ at $2880 min^{-1}$.

Figure S.14.: Logarithmic spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ε at selected radii for $1 L h^{-1}$ at $3690 min^{-1}$.

Figure S.15.: Logarithmic spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ϵ at selected radii for $10 L h^{-1}$ at $3690 min^{-1}$.

Figure S.16.: Logarithmic spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ϵ at selected radii for $20 L h^{-1}$ at $3690 min^{-1}$.

Figure S.17.: Logarithmic spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ϵ at selected radii for $40 L h^{-1}$ at $3690 min^{-1}$.

Figure S.18.: Logarithmic spatial distribution of turbulent dissipation rate ϵ at selected radii for $80 L h^{-1}$ at $3690 min^{-1}$.

Table S.6.: Radii of observation.

Operating Point	r (mm)	Name
0	10.54	r_{Hub}
1	11.12	
2	11.70	
3	12.28	
4	12.87	r_{Mid}
5	13.45	
6	14.03	
7	14.61	
8	15.19	r_{Tip}
9	15.77	
10	16.36	